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Research Article

**ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY: FREQUENCY AND
PERCENTAGE IN NEONATAL APHYXIA CASES, FIGURES
FROM NEONATAL ICU**Saeed Ahmed Shaikh¹, Abdul Hameed Radhan², Muhammad Asim³, Agha Shabbir Ali⁴,
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Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Neonatal asphyxia is a common emergency of neonatal nursery associated with high mortality and morbidity. We aimed this piece of research work on assessing the frequency and percentage of acute kidney injury in neonates presenting with neonatal asphyxia at NICU of Lahore General Hospital, Punjab, Pakistan. There were 270 cases in total admitted as neonatal asphyxia and AKI was found in 143(52.96%) neonates out of which 49(34.27%) were observed in Stage-3, while stage-2 AKI was present in 58(40.56%) neonates whereas sage-1 of acute kidney injury seen in 36(25.17%) neonates and 127(47.04%) neonates did show AKI.

Conclusion: Acute kidney injury was present in 52.96% (143) cases of neonatal asphyxia and it was not seen in 47.04% (127) cases.

Key Words: Acute Kidney Injury, Asphyxia, Neonates, Serum Creatinine

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute kidney injury is among the common most issues of neonatal ICUs. The normal neonatal GFR (glomerular filtration rate) is around 1 ml/min/kg of body weight that is sufficient for normal development and growth [1]. AKI (Acute kidney injury) may be defined as a raised serum creatinine level (> 0.3 ml/dl) over 48 hours or a rise of creatinine by 1.5 fold from the base line in the 1st week or reduction in urine volume (< 0.5 ml/kg/hour) for 6 hours[2]. The normal urine volume or output in neonates is 1-3 ml/kg/hour that is all void at the 1st day of life irrespective of gestational age [3]. The etiology of AKI can be divided into 1, Pre-renal which includes asphyxia, dehydration, sepsis, 2, Renal which may include renal congenital anomalies and direct kidney damage of any nature and 3, post renal where the pathology lies after the kidney like neurogenic bladder and posterior urethral valve etc [4,5]. The prevalence of AKI is reported to be from 8%-24% in neonates by various western studies [6]. Birth Asphyxia causes reduced blood supply to the kidneys that proves the ischemic insult to the renal tissue leading to the development of AKI mediated by multiple pathways [7]. Birth asphyxia is responsible for 23% to 40% neonatal deaths in developing countries while the figure less than 0.1% in well-developed nations as a virtue of their health serves [8,]. An estimation by WHO reported 4 million neonatal emergencies occurring due to asphyxia every year that turns into neonatal death for 1.2 million neonates each year and others subsequently go into other forms of complication like cerebral palsy, developmental delay and epilepsy [9,10]. The main pathogenesis of neonatal

asphyxia is the abnormalities of gas exchange (Oxygen and Carbon) across the placenta but other secondary reasons are responsible which can be further categorized into various sub categories [11, 12]. This work was arranged to assess frequency and percentage of acute renal injury cases in neonatal patients presenting with asphyxia.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted in neonatal ICU of Lahore general hospital on neonates with asphyxia of both male and female gender. Ethical approval and written consent was managed before conduction of study, required information was obtained on proforma, lab test , APGAR score was done .Data analysis carried on SPSS version 22, simple frequency and percentage was calculated.

RESULTS:

In this study total 270 newborns with history of birth asphyxia were included. Among these neonates 173(64%) were male and 97(36%) were Female Out of this 95 male with AKI and 78 with no AKI and 49 females with AKI and 48 with no AKI respectively. APGAR score was noted for all neonates. There were 143(52.96%) neonates with AKI 6(4.19%) neonates whose APGAR was 3, 49 (34.26%) neonates APGAR was 4, 51(35.66%) neonates APGAR score was 5 and 37(25.87%)65 neonates APGAR score was 6 remaining 127(47.07%) neonates with no AKI

There were 49(34.27%) neonates in Stage-3, 58(40.56%) neonates were in stage-2 acute kidney injury and 36(25.17%) neonates were in stage-1 acute kidney injury.

Table-I: Frequency and percentage of neonatal cases of AKI and non-AKI

S. No	Parameters	Males	Females	Total
1.	AKI Present	95(35.19%)	48 (18.15%)	143(52.96%)
2.	AKI Absent	78(28.89%)	49 (17.78%)	127(47.04%)
3.	Total	173(64%)	97(36%)	270(100%)

Figure-I: Distribution of AKI and non-AKI cases in male and female neonates

Table-II: Frequency and percentage of neonates in 3 AKI stages

S. No	Parameters	Frequency/Percentage
1.	AKI Stage-I	36 (25.17%)
2.	AKI Stage-II	58(40.56%)
3.	AKI Stage-III	49 (34.27%)
4.	Total	143(52.96%)

Figure-II: Pie chart of different stages of AKI in study population

Table-III: APGAR Score with Frequency and percentage of AKI and non AKI cases

S. No	APGAR Score	AKI Cases	Non-AKI cases	Total
1.	3	6 (4.19%)	4 (3.15%)	10(3.70%)
2.	4	49 (34.26%)	9 (7.09%)	58 (21.48%)
3.	5	51(35.66%)	61(48.03%)	102(37.78%)
4.	6	37(25.87%)	53 (41.73%)	90 (33.34%)
5.	Total	143(52.96%)	127(47.04%)	270(100%)

Figure-III: Bar charts of the AKI and Non-AKI cases

DISCUSSION:

Amardiyanto *et al* (2013) in their study found prevalence of AKI as 63% that is almost consistent to AKI prevalence in our study [13]. Aggarwal *et al* (2005) reported 56% cases of acute renal failure in their neonatal population suffering from asphyxia that is also nearly resembling with our study findings [14]. Muhammad Ashraf *et al* (2011) in their 80 asphyxia cases based study reported 36 (45%) cases of acute renal failure that is bit lower than our findings [15]. An Indian study conducted by Gupta *et al* (2005) reported 47.1% renal failure in a similar study that is approximately consistent with us [16]. Nouri S *et al* (2008) reported 17.2% AKI cases developed among their study neonates that is inconsistent to our findings [17]. S Kaur *et al* (2011) in a cohort study neonates of severe birth asphyxia 47.1% neonates developed acute kidney injury [18]. Our study as well as other studies showed that neonates presenting with asphyxia are at higher risk of developing acute renal failure so care should be given promptly along with other management.

CONCLUSION:

Acute kidney injury was present in 52.96% (143) cases of neonatal asphyxia and it was not seen in 47.04% (127) cases.

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